

Ecuador first CLEWs approach of the electricity sector focus in Climate Change Policies

- Guillermo Fernández S, United Nation Development Programme/Minister of Environment, Water and Ecology Transition, Ecuador

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Key words

- **hydropower, electricity source, integrated modelling**

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Executive Summary

Ecuador have developed its energy transition taking advantage of its enormous potential of hydro energy, however, the change in precipitation due to climate change is an opportunity to explore other sources of energy and its impact. In 2050 in a water restriction scenario the hydro energy show that as a necessity of fill additional 10% of electricity generation with fuel oil generation in front of the BAU with no effects in Land and Water. In the LT scenario (with 9% Electricity demand increase and demand for biofuels) solar PV will cover 12% of the new electricity matrix in 2050, the land required will increase by approximate of 310 km² (0.1% of national territory) for energy crops and power plants.

Recommendation. The results solar pv and biomass (sugarcane) requirements of land use should be analysed at regional level with a more detailed CLEWs model, taking account that the location for each commodity will be different in terms land categories.

1. Introduction:

From 2008-2018, Ecuador invested approximately 12 000 million dollars (De la Paz Vela & Romero, 2024) to strengthen the electricity sector due to 2009s blackouts. As a result, the installed Capacity grow up from 4470 MW in 2008 to 7513 MW (Fig.1) (68% of increase) in 2018 most the added capacity installed was Hydropower to achieve more than 80% of renewable electricity generation in the main electricity grid (Sistema Nacional Interconectado - SNI) (ARCONEL, 2024).

Fig.1 Ecuador's Installed Capacity 2008-2018 (ARCONEL, 2025)

Since 2017, Ecuador achieved its renewable energy goal (Fig,2). In 2019, Minsitery of Environment and Water present the National Determinated Contribution, and the hydro energy power represented the 90% of GHG emissions reduction (MAAE, 2021). However. In 2024, due to a severe drought, Ecuador presented planned power cuts (blackouts) from 8 to 14 hours from September to December, this event could be reflecting this year electricity generation (Fig. 3) (ARCONEL, 2025) (BBC, 2024).

Fig.2 Ecuador’s electricity generation and renewable energy index at SNI 2018-2024 (ARCONEL, 2025)

The main aim is understanding the cost-effective alternatives that Ecuador have in a water scarcity scenario in hydropower plants generation and how to fill the gap diversifying the electricity generation matrix with the LT LEDS scenario. This scenario also provides insights of CLEWs analysis in mid-term and the necessity of the resources to contribute implementation of climate change policy.

2. Methodology

In this research, the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) analysis was developed using the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) tool. The flexibility of OSeMOSYS to adapt CLEWs variables allows an integrated analysis (Ramos, et al., 2022). The CLEWs modelling methodology allowed for an integral analysis of technology-specific challenges, resources requirements and their implications for climate change policy decision-making.

The Ecuador’s Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided by Climate Compatible Growth within the served as the baseline model (CCG, 2023), incorporating for the scenarios the energy demand estimated to the Long-Term Low Emissions Development Strategy (LEDS) know as Plan de Mitigación al Cambio Climático (2024). Additionally, agriculture and water data were sourced from Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organisation for Economic and Co-operation and Development (OECD) databases.

Three scenarios were developed: Baseline, HYDRO, and LTS. The **Baseline** scenario represents the current state with current policy or resource constraints. The **HYDRO** scenario introduces a restriction of water resource in the same magnitude as the drought presented in 2024. The **LTS** scenario analyzes the electricity matrix and land use within an

increase of electricity demand, driven by electrification initiatives in the transportation, residential, commercial, and industrial sectors. This increase amounts to 9% compared to the previously mentioned scenarios. Additionally, a greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions cap was applied to ensure that at least the 8% reduction target set in Ecuador's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) is maintained.

3. Results

This modelling exercise explored the following research question:

What are the alternatives for Ecuador to achieve its climate change goals under water restrictions scenario in its hydro energy power plants?

The results highlighted distinct paths across the three scenarios: Baseline, HYDRO, and LTS, each offering valuable insights into key aspects of the transition under water restriction:

- In the Baseline, following the guidelines of the electricity sector planning, Ecuador will keep more a percentage of 80 to 90 percent of renewable energy index for electricity generation in the grid. It is important to notice that the projection maintain natural gas, and fuel oil power plant running to stabilize the electricity system. (Fig. 3)
- In the HYDRO scenario, Ecuador reduces face a reduction of 62% of reduction in its capacity factor of hydro power energy plants and cover this gap with Light and heavy Fuel Oil Power Plant (Fig.3).
- In the LTS scenario, Ecuador increases the electricity consumption up to 208 PJ due to transition to electric transport and strengthen biofuels consumption. This scenario is market by the emission restriction in the same rate as the NDC commitment filling the gap with solar energy. The solar energy (yellow and blue block of Fig.3) covers a 12% of the electricity requirements.

4. Discussion:

Between Baseline and HYDRO scenario, it is evident that the main measure to address water restrictions is replacing hydropower generation with electricity produced by internal combustion engines. This suggests that, although there are cheaper and more environmentally friendly alternatives, such as natural gas, Ecuador faces specific challenges in adopting them. Since the country exports most of the Fuel Oil it produces, developing the necessary infrastructure and securing a stable supply of natural gas would require significant investment and time. Given these constraints, the most practical and cost-effective solution for Ecuador is to use domestically produced Fuel Oil, which is more readily available and easier to integrate into the existing energy system.

On the other hand, when comparing Baseline and HYDRO scenarios with LTS, some key differences can be observed. As a result, the model optimizes the energy mix and indicates that solar power would be the best option for new installations, covering approximately 13% of the 2050 total electricity demand. Given the restrictions on generation capacity and emission limits to maintain the NDC target, the most cost-effective option is the installation of hydropower, despite its low-capacity factor. However, this choice is offset by the high upfront investment required in previous years to sustain electricity demand.

Since biofuel and solar energy initiatives were incorporated into the LTS scenario, it can be inferred that the land required for these technologies will increase over time. This is because both biofuel production and solar power installations depend on significant land use, either for crop cultivation or for solar panel deployment. In this context, although the additional land needed for these technologies is estimated at 310 km², this area would account for approximately 28% of the projected land dedicated to coffee crop cultivation by 2050. This highlights the importance of carefully planning land use to balance renewable energy expansion with agricultural needs and environmental sustainability.

As potential improvements to the CLEWs model presented in this report, it is important to note that the current national-level analysis may underestimate land use results. This is because the regions where crops are grown and where solar potential is highest have distinct dynamics that are not fully captured in the aggregated model. For this reason, it is necessary to further refine the model by disaggregating it at least into Ecuador's three main regions, allowing for a more accurate representation of local conditions and resource interactions.

Additionally, another improvement would be to include fossil fuel commodities in the model. This would provide a clearer understanding of how fossil fuel consumption is expected to decrease as electrification initiatives are implemented, offering a more comprehensive analysis of the energy transition and its impact on the national energy mix.

5. Conclusion:

This first approach did not aim to re-examine the long-term goal if the climate change policy in Ecuador but give a new vision of what could be the integral implication under water restriction hypothesis.

It can be observed that Ecuador's high dependence on fossil fuels may lead to an increase in their use within the electricity generation mix. While this approach can help ensure a stable power supply, efforts should be made to keep emissions low to meet international commitments for emission reductions.

As an alternative, the LTS Scenario shows that solar energy emerges as the most cost-effective option, primarily due to Ecuador's current limitations in securing a reliable supply of natural gas.

Additionally, an increase in greenhouse gas reduction measures through biofuels and solar energy could have a significant impact, especially when compared to the projected use of smaller-scale crops. This highlights the importance of carefully planning policies to ensure the orderly integration of these initiatives into the energy and land-use framework.

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